

The adoption of Human Resource Information System (HRIS) and employees engagement: evidence from United Arab Emirates

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The purpose of this paper is to examine the relationships among Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS)—transactional, relational and transformational—and user satisfaction and intention to engage. It also investigates the mediating role of user satisfaction in the relationship between HRIS attributes and intention to engage. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire of various public organizations in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structured equation modeling (SEM) methods, the results indicate that HRIS attributes positively influence user satisfaction and intention to engage. The paper's originality and value come from its theoretical contribution to literature in the context of Middle East. The theoretical and practical implications of these findings are also discussed.

keywords: United Arab Emirates, public sector organizations, human resource information system, user satisfaction, intention to engage

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Introduction

Since the late 1990s, information technology (IT) and communications (ITC) have significantly influenced society. This has come about primarily because of the development of the Internet. IT can make public sector organizations more efficient and effective in carrying out various operations (Luo 2009). Public employees, as the contributors to efficiency and effectiveness, should have the required e-readiness. IT provides automatic means for handling the information; public sector employees use this information to shape organizational change and to transform their strategic role through the adoption of IT (Haines & Lafleur 2008). IT is not only the vital element of human resources information systems (HRIS), but also information validity and reliability and, ultimately, its utility for users. The technology is used in the HR departments to provide benefits ranging from the publication of information and automation of transactions as the enabler of the transformation face of HRM within the organization (Al Dmour & Al

Zu'bi 2014, Qadir & Agrawal 2017). The human resource function is an information system that requires adequate access to modern technology and the ability to reconstitute the governance mechanism. Capable and highly qualified human resources employees are needed to coordinate the internal and external services factors to be able to handle the demand for services (Wimmer 2002). Almost all HR processes can be done by using HRIS, which can benefit the organization in several ways. For instance, as an implication of HRIS, the automation of tasks and processes reduces the use of resources (financial, material, and human). Reduction of HR costs, less usage of paper, and assisting managers in the HR process are some examples of reduction of resource usage. Although attention has been given to studying HRIS's impact on HR function in Arab countries (Al Dmour & Zu'bi 2014), only limited studies have been conducted in the UAE. These studies are not comprehensive and examine only some individual-related topics of human resource activities (Al Athmay et al. 2020, Budhwar & Mellahi 2007). Existing literature investigates the impact of HRIS in terms of its effect on the operational, relational, and transformational aspects of the organization (Nayak et al. 2017, Parry 2011). However, there is a lack of research on HRM in the Arab world in general (Forstenlechner 2010, Rees et al. 2007) and in the Gulf countries in particular. In addition, there is minimal research on HRIS, specifically related to the UAE's public sector organizations (Reddick 2009). The difficulty of finding reliable data and conducting research in the region may be contributing factors to this deficit (Al Athmay et al. 2020). The existing studies were conducted either to show the benefits and barriers of HRIS adoption, or to investigate the determinants that influence the adoption of HRIS, or to explore the valuable outcomes in terms of efficiency and effectiveness of adopting HRIS.

To our knowledge, this study is the first attempt in UAE and probably one of few attempts in developing countries to research the impact of HRIS on the operational, relational, and transformational aspects of HR. In this study, user satisfaction is treated as an intermediate variable in terms of its effect on enhancing the employee's engagement through HRIS and how this engagement varied in selected HRIS attributes. This study is significant because it presents an integrated conceptual model that not only focuses on the direct effect of some characteristics of HRIS on user satisfaction but also on the effect of user satisfaction on the engagement of employees in terms of how HRIS contributed to meeting the needs of employees. Additionally, it examines these attributes' direct and indirect effects as the variable *satisfaction* mediates them. This study is also designed to fill the gap in studies undertaken in the Arab region.

This study investigates the impact of HRIS on the practices of human resource departments in the United Arab Emirates public sector organizations. Specifically, it examines the perceptions of public sector employees regarding the types of information provided by HR departments. It explores how different kinds of information, namely transactional, relational, and transformational, affect users' satisfaction and how users' satisfaction enhances employee engagement with HRIS services. It presents the results of a survey of sampled employees in UAE public sector organizations. The research is based primarily on a quantitative approach using a questionnaire survey to collect data across multiple settings pertaining to the research hypotheses. We conducted a field study of human resource management service users in the UAE and tested the proposed model using the structural equation modeling (SEM) technique. The authors of this research investigate three different orientations in which public sector organizations engage their employees through HRIS. The first is the transactional (operational) approach, where activities are undertaken to meet the short-term needs of employees who want to take part in the HR efforts of the organization. The second is a relational approach based on improving HR's external relationship with other parties within the organization. It is during this stage that shared interest and trust in the HRM programs are developed. The third is the transformational approach, which aims to redefine the scope and function of HR in the organization to focus more on strategic issues and to facilitate the positive impacts of HRM on the organization, employees, and society (Athmay et al. 2020, Knies et al. 2018). Research for this paper took place in the UAE, a country that has achieved remarkable social and

economic performance. In all e-government indicators, the UAE fares well above most developing countries in general and other Arab countries in particular (Al Athmay & Rahim 2013). Therefore, this study addresses the gaps in knowledge left by previous research. This study expands the scope of literature by examining the United Arab Emirates as a transitional economy. The study mainly attempts to answer the following questions: (1) What is the direct effect on user satisfaction of HRIS attributes? (2) What is the direct effect of user satisfaction on user intention to engage with the HRIS of the organization? (3) What is the direct effect of HRIS attributes on the intention to support the organization's HRIS? and (4) What is the role of user satisfaction as a mediator on behavioral intention to engage with HRIS of the organization?

In the next section, we develop hypotheses followed by methodology and analysis. Then we present the findings and discussion along with implications for managers and direction for future research.

Theory and Hypotheses Development

Our research model is based upon DeLone and Mclean's (2003) updated the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model (Al Athmay et al. 2020). Utilizing these models, the present research model adopted three attributes of HRIS's information: transactional, relational, and transformational, and investigated their impact on user satisfaction and employees' intention to engage. We join other researchers in suggesting that transactional, relational and transformational's information are a subset of HRIS's system quality (Al Athmay et al. 2020, Chakraborty & Abu Mansor 2013).

Figure 1. HRIS linking Satisfaction and Engagement

Source: the authors

Based on UTAUT, the research model used variables such as user satisfaction and intention to use, in addition to the three types of HRIS variables: transactional, relational, and transformational. HRIS attributes identified in this research cannot be considered complete. Although other dimensions, such as culture, trust, awareness, organizational, environmental, etc., are of great interest, they are not included due to the length of the survey and concerns regarding the parsimony of this research. The research model shown in Figure 1 was simplified to offer a complete picture of some selected influential factors in the adoption of HRIS services in the UAE's public sector organizations from an employee perspective.

Human Resource Information System (HRIS): Transactional – User Satisfaction

Studies in HRIS have highlighted three main benefits of HRIS adoption; namely, the transactional, transformational, and relational aspects of HRIS (Qadir & Agrawal 2017). The transactional element of IT utilization in HRM is intended to improve the organization's operational efficiency and meet the needs of the employees and managers in terms of the automation of HR records about diverse HRM activities.

Transactional attribute deals with operational and administrative functions such as Payroll, record keeping, and benefits calculations. Transactional is supposed to meet the short-term needs of employees who want to participate in the organization's HR efforts. Many of the functions of the human resources department are routine and repetitive. Some examples are payroll, record keeping, and benefits calculations (Parry 2011, Shrivastava & Shaw 2003). HRM systems easily automate these operations, thus reducing costs and improving efficiency. So, we assume that transaction function positively influences the user's acceptance and satisfaction (AlAlmeri 2017, Al Dmour & Zu'bi 2014). So, we propose the following hypothesis.

H1a. Transactional services have a positive effect on user satisfaction.

HRIS: Relational – User Satisfaction

Studies on the relational aspect of HRIS have highlighted the extent to which HR enhances services provided to managers and employees, improving the relationship and building trust in practices of which organizational members have little knowledge. And the effect of HR practices on relationships is the process within the organization, producing better-informed HR decisions (Ball 2001, Reddick 2009). These studies have neither addressed the link of HRIS to user satisfaction nor investigated the impact of HRIS on employee intention to engage through the mediating factor of user satisfaction. This research addresses this gap. While the operational impact of HRM systems focuses on internally improving the human resources function, the relationship impact crosses over to other departments and connects them. It allows people across the organization to access HR data, resulting in improved and more informed decision-making (Ball 2001, Kovach & Cathcart 1999). Managers and employees can perform HR activities themselves, thereby reducing response times, improving service levels, and bringing more informed decision-making. The impact of relational aspects of the daily HR function can increase commitment and further engagement among employees (Qamari et al. 2022, Shrivastava & Shaw 2003). Our next hypothesis is:

H1b. Relational services have a positive effect on user satisfaction.

HRIS: Transformational – User Satisfaction

The transformational attribute is concerned with HR strategies in areas such as knowledge management and organizational change and taking the organization further steps to produce more value for itself and society. It is agreed that IT within the HR department improves efficiency and the information flow across the organization (relationship impact). The HR department takes center stage when the transformational impact comes into the picture. The transformational effect of HRM systems is an extension of the scope and function of the HR department to include a strong strategic focus. Jobs are much more flexible and are designed around skills, roles, and projects rather than stable tasks. It allows for shared information within and outside of the organization and ensures more accuracy in the core functions of HRM. It activates and develops employees, furthering their engagement to produce more excellent value for the organization and society. It is increasingly involved in fundamental changes within the HR department and across the organization in how they view the business (Nayak et al. 2017, Obeidat 2012). So we propose:

H1c. Transformational services have a positive effect on user satisfaction.

User Satisfaction and Intention to Engage

User satisfaction is used as a mediating variable to either boost or thwart employees' engagement with HRIS within the organization. Even though a great deal of attention has been given to the study of HRIS

success, we do not find any study investigating these variables (transactional, relational, transformational, user satisfaction, and intention to engage) in the region in general and UAE particularly (Sanayei et al. 2008). Although literature exists on HRIS and satisfaction (Coursey & McCreary 2005, Reddick 2009), the impact of user satisfaction on employee engagement is missing. However, users' experience and attitudes with the application of HRIS would add enjoyment and acceptability to the users, increase engagement, and further the trust and commitment of employees. Therefore, this research adds to the limited pool of studies that have been carried out in developing countries. This study was designed because the applicability of a model may vary in different nations. As a preliminary investigation, the current paper focuses only on attributes—transactional, relational, transformational—and investigates their impact on user satisfaction and the employees' intention to engage. So, we propose the following hypothesis:

H2. User satisfaction leads to engagement in the use of HRIS.

Mediating Effects of User Satisfaction on Intention to Engage

The third group of hypotheses deals with the total effects of HRIS attributes on intention to engage. Besides the direct impact, HRIS attributes (transactional, relational, and transformational) also directly affect the intention to engage through user satisfaction. It was predicted that any relationship between these attributes and intention to engage would be mediated by user satisfaction. We expected to find a direct path from HRIS attributes to intention to engage, mediated by user satisfaction. User satisfaction has been widely cited as a measure of the success and effectiveness of HRIS. DeLone and McLean (2003) and Gupta and Saxena (2010) have studied the potential benefits of the adoption of HRIS and found that HRIS can achieve better client, enhance user satisfaction, and achieve efficiency. Lazim et al. (2023) studied the usefulness of information and communication technology in the human resources department of the Malaysian government. They found that timesaving, cost saving, and system quality are the most significant factors affecting user satisfaction using the HRMIS. Thus, the findings of this study should be able to provide awareness of the importance of using HRMIS among public servants. Khashman and Al-Ryalat (2015) studied user satisfaction in a data warehouse. They found that the automation of HR positively affects user satisfaction, including support to end users, information quality, accuracy, and fulfillment of users' needs. From these studies, we can predict that the moderating effect of user satisfaction on HRIS attributes (Transactional, Relational, and Transformational) would be positively related to end users' intention to engage. The research study proposes the following hypotheses for the effects of the mediating variable (user satisfaction) on the intention to engage.

HRIS: Transactional – User Engagement

Transactional services are related to operational and administrative functions such as payroll, record keeping, and benefits calculations. The critical results of the transactional function are to improve operational productivity and provide support automated services for the employees. The implication of this function is to enhance users' acceptance and satisfaction. Some literature on Electronic human resources has studied the impact of transactional function on the efficiency and effectiveness of human resources departments (AlAlmeri 2017, Reddick 2009). These studies have neither addressed the link of HRIS to user satisfaction nor investigated the impact of HRIS on employee intention to engage through the mediating factor of user satisfaction. Thus, we can hypothesize a positive link between users' satisfaction with HRIS services, such as transactional, and users' intention to engage.

H3a. Transactional services have a positive effect on user engagement

HRIS: Relational – User Engagement

As a part of the HRIS quality system, relational function allows employees across the organization to access the HR data, resulting in improved and more informed decision making. The impact of relational aspects of the daily HR function can increase the commitment and further the satisfaction and engagement of the employees (Al Dmour & Zu'bi 2014). These studies have neither addressed the link of HRIS attributes (Transactional, Relational, and Transformational) to user satisfaction nor investigated the impact of HRIS on employee intention to engage through the mediating factor of user satisfaction. Thus, we can predict a positive link between users' satisfaction with HRIS services, such as relational, and users' intention to engage. Our next hypothesis is:

H3b. Relational services have a positive effect on user engagement.

HRIS: Transformational – User Engagement

Transformational attribute of HRIS involves structural changes in the scope and function of the HR department and aligning employee activities with the needs of organizational strategies and customers or clients. According to some studies on the benefits of electronic human resources (EHRM) management, jobs are more flexible and designed based on employees' skills, roles, and projects. EHRM allows for shared information within and outside of the organization, ensuring more accuracy in the core functions of HRM (AlAmeri 2017). These studies have fallen short of the impact of EHRM and the effects of these benefits on the employees' intention to engage. However, they indirectly postulate a positive influence on users' acceptance and satisfaction. In this study, the HRIS transformational attribute is to develop and activate employees, which in turn furthers the employees' engagement to produce greater value for the organization and society. So we finally hypothesize:

H3c. Transformational services have a positive effect on user engagement.

Methodology

Data Collection

The sampling frame for this study is made up of employees working in public sector organizations. The total number of the surveyed public sector organizations is 92. They were chosen from three Emirates: Abu Dhabi, Dubai, and Sharjah. The three emirates were selected because they are the three biggest emirates in the UAE. Three trained people collected the data using a structured questionnaire on a 5-point scale (1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree) from an average of 20 random users of HRIS daily, resulting in an overall sample of 1800. The exclusion of 200 questionnaires with incomplete data resulted in a final usable sample of 1600 responses. The sample consisted of male/female (60%/40%), graduate/diploma (70%/30%), employees between 100 and 500 (85%/10%), and IT experts/other (90%/10%).

Operational Measures of the Variables

Transactional (TRANSACT) relates to the degree to which HRIS is undertaken to automate record-keeping and routine clerical activities such as payroll and benefits administration (Chakraborty & Abu Mansorb 2013). It has seven items. *Relational* (RELATION) relates to the degree to which HRIS influences HR's relationship externally with other parties within the organization, thus allowing HR to enhance service by providing managers and employees with remote access to HR databases, supporting their HR-related decisions (Reddick 2009). It has seven items. *Transformational* (TRANSFOR) relates to involving fundamental changes in the scope and function of the HR department and aligning employee activities with the needs of customers or clients (Al Athmay 2020). It has seven items. *User Satisfaction* (USER_SAT) relates to online information and services and the level of satisfaction with these offerings (DeLone & McLean 2003). It has five items. *Intention to engage* (INT_ENGA) relates to the ability of the HRIS system

to positively impact employees' attitudes towards continuous use of HRIS services. It has three items (Al Athmay et al. 2016).

Analyses

Table 1 reports factors and reliability statistics. Values above .70 indicate the reliability of factors (Gefen et al. 2000). We use Harman's one-factor test to test the common method variance. Results show that only one factor emerged and explained less than 50% of the variance (42.40% ie Eigenvalue 2.6). We used SEM to analyze and test the hypotheses. With 29 observed variables, there are $(29 \times 30) / 2 = 435$ observations; the number of parameters to be estimated is 65, including the variances of 29 variables (21 exogenous and 8 indigenous variables, ie the disturbance), 29 direct loading on each latent variable, and seven direct effects. Further, three error covariance were set to free. Thus, the model degrees of freedom are $435 - 65 - 3 = 367$. Since the number of observations is greater than the number of parameters to be estimated, we conclude that the HRIS model is over-identified and can be tested statistically. Our analysis indicates the observed Chi-square ($\chi^2 = 1067.82$), degree of freedom ($df = 367$, $p = .00$), $RMSEA = .04$, $GFI = .99$, $AGFI = .93$, $NFI = .98$, $NNFI = .97$, and $CFI = .99$. Our model represents a good fit.

Table 1. Factors and Reliability

Factors	# of items	Cronbach (α)	Eigenvalues
Transactional (TRANSACT)	7	.86	2.76
Relational (RELATION)	7	.82	1.76
Transformational (TRANSFOR)	7	.90	1.49
User Satisfaction (USER_SAT)	5	.85	1.24
Intention to engage (INT_ENGA)	3	.79	1.16

Table 2 reports correlations below .9, indicating no common method bias in the data. The measures have the convergent validity. The average variances extracted were above the recommended .50 level (Hair et al. 1992), meaning their hypothesized factors accounted for more than one-half of the variances observed in these items.

Table 2. Constructs Correlations, AVE Values

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1 TRANSACT	4.89	1.34	1				
2 RELATION	5.11	1.02	.73**	1			
3 TRANSFOR	5.11	1.54	.64**	.64**	1		
4 USER_SAT	4.97	1.07	.72**	.57**	.59**	1	
5 INT_ENGA	5.99	1.33	.81**	.68**	.63**	.75**	1
AVE/ \sqrt AVE			.85/.92	.72/.85	.69/.83	.80/.89	.77/.88
Composite Reliability			.86	.86	.87	.90	.80

** $p < .01$ (2-tailed)

Results and Discussion

Table 3 suggests that $H1a$ ($\beta = .19$, $p = .01$), $H1b$ ($\beta = .28$, $p = .01$), and $H1c$ ($\beta = .42$, $p = .05$), are supported. This result is not surprising since a number of researchers highlighted the positive association among RELATION, TRANSACT and, TRANSFOR, and USER_SAT. For example, Yung-Shen (2014) indicates that the effect of structural capital on user satisfaction was fully mediated through relational, suggesting that

frequent communication between IT units and users may not necessarily lead to user satisfaction unless relational is well developed. The study empirically examined the impact of transactional and relational customers on user satisfaction in e-commerce in Taiwan. Based on AlAmeri (2017) study, the Implications of implementing electronic human resource management in Abu Dhabi (UAE) are that EHRM provides a framework to automate key HR services like employee onboarding, training, payroll, benefits, administrative support, and documentation submission, such as time sheets, leave of absence and performance review. In addition, he found that EHRM changed the nature of interactions among HR staff, line managers, and employees from a pure face-to-face relationship to a technology-mediated one.

Table 3. Path Coefficients for Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficients	p-value	Results
H1a	transaction → satisfaction	.19	.01	Supported
H1b	relational → satisfaction	.28	.01	Supported
H1c	transformational → satisfaction	.42	.05	Supported
H2	satisfaction → engagement	.60	.00	Supported
H3a	Transaction → engagement	.37	.01	Supported
H3b	Relational → engagement	.25	.00	Supported
H3c	Transformational → engagement	.45	.01	Supported

H2 ($\beta=.60$, $p=.00$) is supported. This is consistent with the majority of empirical studies conducted in human resources literature. For instance, Rehman et al. (2012) reported a positive effect of user satisfaction on the intention of citizens to adopt e-government services. Further, Sambasivan et al. (2010) reported that e-government and the use of procurement electronic systems in e-government have a strong positive relationship between the user's satisfaction and the intention to engage with actual use. Although literature exists on HRIS and satisfaction, the impact of user satisfaction on employee engagement seems to be missing. This literature has touched on the potential benefits of adopting HRIS and found that HRIS can achieve better clients, enhance user satisfaction, and achieve efficiency (Coursey & McCreary 2005). However, we can say that users' experience and attitudes with the application of HRIS would add enjoyment and acceptability to the users, furthering the trust and commitment of employees and increasing engagement.

H3a ($\beta=.37$, $p=.01$), *H1b* ($\beta=.25$, $p=.00$), and *H1c* ($\beta=.45$, $p=.05$) are supported. This result is not surprising since a number of researchers highlighted the positive association among *RELATION*, *TRANSACT* and, *TRANSFOR*, and *INT_ENGA*. Intention to engage refers to the customer's perception that the service was intrinsically enjoyable (Trevino & Webster 1992). The research indicates that the intention to engage can positively impact the use of technology environments for use), other software use, and website use (Novak et al. 2000). Therefore, intention to engage is positively and significantly related to the *RELATION*, *TRANSACT* and *TRANSFOR*. In other words, intention to engage significantly influences HRIS.

Managerial and Theoretical Implications

The study developed a theoretical rationale and empirically tested the relationships among human resource information systems (HRIS) in terms of (transactional, relational, and transformational), user satisfaction, and intention to engage. It also investigates the mediating role of user satisfaction. Our findings suggest that public organizations striving to enhance HRIS should pay attention to the critical role of user satisfaction. In addition, understanding HRIS factors (transactional, relational, and transformational) helps policymakers formulate and develop strategies to increase the intention of the citizens to engage either to acquire information or to conduct transactions on the public website.

Aggarwal and Kapoor (2012) mentioned that HRIS helps the management and HR department and assists the employees in several ways.

Further, managers operating in the public sector can exploit the findings of this study by developing an appropriate HRIS and enhancing technology diffusion in areas under their authority. Many researchers have encouraged using HRIS to increase the overall decision-making efficiency of an organization's management and improve the intention to engage. HRIS helps the HR department to develop a centralized database that provides the public organization with all necessary information and opportunities for different reports. In addition, HRIS eliminates paper forms and errors caused by human factors and is environmentally friendly (Chakraborty & Abu Mansour 2013). The results of this study imply that a user satisfaction will be beneficial for attracting increased users of the public sector information systems such as online services by providing up-to-date information, and this, in turn, will increase user satisfaction and, consequently, the intention to engage through technology. Furthermore, the increased usage of human resources information systems can generate more benefits, such as operational excellence, cost and time savings, increased effectiveness, and better quality of public services (Al Athmay et al. 2016). For the employees, HRIS provides the possibility of independent access to data, which often means working in one software window and keeping automatic tracking and reminders of business obligations and events. In some organizations, employees can also attend online training courses to develop their skills and knowledge. As a result, it encourages employees to make decisions and initiatives on the basis of information obtained in the HRIS system.

According to Oliveira and Martins (2010), technology readiness is dependent on an organization's technology infrastructure and IT human resources. Based on IT expertise, skills, and knowledge that they use to build a web application, technology infrastructure makes a more accessible base on which internet technologies can be created. HRIS can only become integral if the organization has infrastructure and technical skills. These factors allow the technological capacity of an organization to adopt HRIS (Oliveira & Martins 2010). Conversely, since organizations with superior technology readiness are in a better position to adopt HRIS, companies that do not have robust technology infrastructure and comprehensive IT expertise may not take the risk of adopting HRIS. Several researchers have recognized technological readiness as a significant factor that influences IT adoption (Kwon & Zmud 1987). Also, many researchers have pointed out that IT investments per se do not enhance productivity and performance improvements, but they must be complemented with, for instance, other organizational resources, such as the human and relationship assets, to form what is called HRIS. The HRIS leverages the business processes, resulting in superior and efficient product or service delivery infrastructures and cost-effective and operational systems. When strategically aligned with business functions, it yields performance improvements, translating into sustained competitive advantage in the long run.

Conclusion, Limitations, and Future Research

The level of uncertainty has increased exponentially in the present dynamic business environment. HRIS practices in terms of (transactional, relational, and transformational) have tremendously witnessed themselves as a contributor to the user's satisfaction and enriching intention to engage. Understanding the HIRS and their relationship with user satisfaction and intention to engage will help public organizations achieve excellence in services and in serving society and stakeholders. Achieving user satisfaction, which in turn positively impacts the intention to engage, will facilitate many benefits for HRM, such as a more straightforward process, cheaper, faster, more effective, and more efficient, and increasing the organization's performance. All these benefits of HRIS can be achieved perfectly only if HIRS is adopted or adapted in an organization accurately and more effectively.

The measurements of other attributes of HRIS than user satisfaction and intention to engage can be a possible limitation of the study. Further refinement of HIRS, user satisfaction and intention to engage

scales is needed in future research. It also was noticed that most studies were done in Europe and the USA and outside developing countries; thus, this opens a perspective to examine the future HRIS adoption in different geographical areas. The other limitation is that data were collected from only three Emirates in the UAE (Sharjah, Dubai, and Abu Dhabi). Therefore, caution should be considered when generalizing this study's findings to other UAE Emirates. It would be exciting to conduct a future comprehensive work that includes the intention to engage the citizens in all seven Emirates and compare it with the findings of this study.

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